

How to Cite (APA): Çetinkaya, A., et al. (2025). Exploring the open-source concept to enhance the learning and exploration curve of ai architecture. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 342–352). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

Exploring the Open-Source Concept to Enhance the Learning and Exploration Curve of AI Architecture

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KEYWORDS - Open-Source Dataset, Data Visualization, Deep Learning, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Python, Artificial Intelligence (AI)

ABSTRACT

The architecture of artificial intelligence has transformed the foundational principles behind the development of digital solutions across diverse fields, such as education, healthcare, and defense. This transformation is most evident in the processes of data analysis and the construction of predictive models for forecasting outcomes. Successfully implementing such architecture requires an understanding of the learning curve and the techniques for deploying AI frameworks. This learning phase, particularly during the pre-production stage of lifecycle development, often demands various resources, with three key pillars being crucial: data, algorithms, and digital tools or libraries. This study investigates into these three pillars through the perspective of "open-source." It utilizes two open-source datasets—one to develop an "analytical model" using distinct data analysis methods, and the other to create an AI "predictive model" based on the LSTM algorithm. Both models are built using open-source tools and frameworks. The study's findings provide a foundational example, showcasing how leveraging open-source datasets, AI models, and libraries or frameworks can effectively: (1) expedite the learning process or exploration necessary for adopting AI architecture as a solution, and (2) support the implementation of AI solutions across various industries as automated approaches. Future research is also recommended.

1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI), whose conceptual roots can be traced back to the question posed by Arf in 1959—"Can machines think, and if so, how?"—has evolved into a rapidly expanding technological domain by 2024. This development enables the effective execution of critical processes such as system design, monitoring, control, and auditing through AI implementations. AI is now central in creating automated systems capable of making swift decisions and producing accurate, reliable outcomes.

Today, algorithms, in conjunction with programming languages, are driving significant technological advancements. The evolution of algorithms, empowered by AI's dynamic structure and learning capabilities, continues to shape emerging technologies across disciplines. With the accelerating pace of technological development, the integration of AI into diverse fields has also surged. AI applications are being deployed in digital transformation projects, strategic military systems, surveillance technologies, agricultural monitoring, information and communication systems, image processing, data analytics, natural language processing, cybersecurity, voice recognition, and more (Ozcan, 2022; Firat, 2024; Turan, 2024; Çetinkaya, 2024).

Selecting the right algorithmic approach for a given problem is crucial for systems composed of algorithms and hardware to function effectively. This selection depends on the integrity of an application. Even the most accurate and comprehensive mathematical models may encounter uncertainties during operation. To address these uncertainties, systems must incorporate space of variables and functions that best reflect human reasoning. This design approach enhances the system's flexibility and efficiency.

AI has transcended its origins as a research concept to become a powerful engine of technological revolution. Table 1 provides a timeline of the evolution of key disciplines—mathematics, astronomy, logic, and metaphysics—that laid the theoretical groundwork for AI. The timeline spans from the year 780 to the present, highlighting major historical milestones in the development of AI concepts. In summary, employing AI architecture as a solution relies on three fundamental pillars: data, algorithms, and digital tools, such as libraries or frameworks.

Table 1. Historical Development Process of Artificial Intelligence Studies

Study Content	Year	Referenced Source
Al-Khwarizmi conducted studies in mathematics, astronomy, and early algorithms.	780	Brezina, 2006; Uyanık, 2022
Al-Jazari pioneered automation, cybernetics, and robotic systems.	1203	Çırak, 2016
Nasir al-Din al-Tusi contributed to astronomy, metaphysics, logic, and mathematics.	1274	Taştan, 2001
Taqi al-Din established the Istanbul observatory and conducted technological studies in astronomy, optics, and automation systems.	1575	Topdemir, 2022
A robotic invention named "Alamet" was developed.	1889	Özşahin, 2017
Research and investigations were conducted on the human brain.	1890	James, 1984
The first image transfer study in image processing was carried out.	1921	McFarlane, 1972
A cryptographic system named Enigma was used for decryption.	1939	Turing, 1940
The first artificial neural network model was introduced.	1943	McCulloch, 1943
Alan Turing proposed the Turing Test for assessing machine intelligence.	1948	Turing, 1948
The Hebbian rule explored the role of neural connectivity in learning.	1949	Hebb, 1949
The concept of adaptive response through random networks was introduced.	1954	Farley, 1954
The term "Artificial Intelligence" was coined.	1955	McCarthy, 1955
Perceptron: A single-layer neural network was developed.	1957	Rosenblatt, 1957

“Can Machines Think and How Do They Think?” was published.	1959	Arf, 1959
ADALINE: A single-layer neural network was created.	1959	Widrow, 1960
Learning Machines concept was introduced.	1965	Nilsson, 1965
Fuzzy Logic theory was introduced.	1965	Zadeh, 1965
Expert Systems were developed.	1970	Allahverdi, 2002
CPU (Central Processing Unit): The first microprocessor Intel 4004 was produced.	1971	Vacroux, 1975
A robot named WABOT-1 was produced.	1973	Kato, 1987
Deep Blue, a chess machine, defeated world champion Garry Kasparov.	1997	Campbell, 2002
CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks): A system for handwritten digit recognition was developed.	1998	LeCun, 1998
ImageNet: An image database with 50 million entries was created.	2009	Deng, 2009
Image processing studies were conducted using GPU (Graphics Processing Unit).	2012	Krizhevsky, 2017
GAN (Generative Adversarial Networks) was introduced to generate synthetic images using AI.	2014	Goodfellow, 2020
DARPA Humanoid Robot Challenge took place.	2015	Spenko, 2018
Autonomous driving levels were implemented in Tesla autonomous vehicles.	2015	Lin, 2018
Google's Teachable Machine introduced a web-based AI subfield.	2017	Google, 2017
Google developed the BERT model for question answering and language inference tasks.	2018	Devlin, 2018
OpenAI introduced a language model (GPT) with 1.5 billion parameters.	2019	Radford, 2019
AI-powered assistants such as Apple Siri, Amazon Alexa, Google Assistant, and Microsoft Cortana were utilized in healthcare.	2021	Yang, 2021
OpenAI released DALL·E, a text-to-image generation model with 12 billion parameters.	2021	Ramesh, 2021
GPT-3 enabled multilingual language processing models.	2022	Yang, 2022
GPT-4 gained the capability of behavioral alignment and adaptability.	2024	Achiam, 2024

The primary objective of this study is to present a showcase example illustrating the use of open-source datasets, AI algorithms, and libraries or frameworks to simplify the learning curve for deploying AI architecture solutions in the form of analytical and predictive models. For the analytical model, data visualization techniques were applied to analyze an open-source dataset, with the findings displayed through intuitive graphical representations. For the predictive model, deep learning techniques, such as LSTM, were utilized to uncover complex patterns in the data and generate time series predictions using another open-source dataset. Open-source libraries and frameworks supported this effort, enabling the integration of open-source datasets, AI models, and tools/frameworks.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 details the materials and methods used in this investigation, including the open-source datasets, AI algorithms, and libraries. Section 3 describes the experimental implementation of open-source tools and libraries on the datasets. Section 4 offers

a general discussion on the showcase example, while Section 5 provides the conclusion and suggests potential directions for future work.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

To develop a digital solution based on AI architecture, it is crucial to ensure that data is organized in a specific form and structure. However, when it comes to learning and testing, obtaining private and relevant data directly from original sources can present significant challenges. Open-source platforms provide an excellent opportunity for researchers and scholars by offering readily available datasets from various industries. Additionally, open-source frameworks and tools supply an extensive range of libraries that can be used to process data and generate either analytical or predictive models. This section highlights three sources corresponding to the three pillars mentioned earlier in the introduction: open-source datasets, algorithms, and libraries/frameworks.

2.1 Open-Source Dataset

Open-source data plays a critical role in AI research. The successful training and accuracy of AI models depend on large and diverse datasets. Open-source datasets provide researchers and developers with free access to valuable data, accelerating project development. Furthermore, they offer standardized benchmarks for testing and comparing AI algorithms. These datasets facilitate model development across various domains, such as healthcare, finance, transportation, and environmental science. The sharing of open data promotes collaboration, fosters innovation, and ensures that research becomes more inclusive and transparent.

The National Smart Cities Data Sharing Platform (ULUSAV) was established to enhance transparency, accountability, and data-driven decision-making by enabling public access to urban data across Türkiye. This platform facilitates the sharing of data provided by municipalities, public institutions, and relevant stakeholders, in compliance with the Personal Data Protection Law and other legal regulations. ULUSAV allows users to access, analyze, and visualize city-related datasets, and to develop applications that contribute to the improvement of urban management and public services. In this study, two datasets obtained from the ULUSAV platform are utilized: one is used to develop an analytical model, while the other serves in building a predictive model (ULUSAV, 2025).

As shown in Figure 1, the dataset includes official records between 2004 and 2023 on quantities of compost produced per ton, materials recycled, fuel quantities, and electricity generated in megawatt-hours (MWh). This dataset is publicly accessible.

	A	B	C	D	E
	Yıl	Üretilen Kompost Miktarı [ton]	İBB Tesislerinde Geri Dönüştürülen Malzeme Miktarı [ton]	Atıktan Türetilmiş Yakıt Miktarı [ton]	Çöp Gazından Üretilen Elektrik Enerjisi Miktarları [MWh]
2	2004	16.861	1.513		5.938
3	2009	10.450	8.454	1.087	70.895
4	2014	17.136	17.425	35.552	336.547
5	2015	18.423	7.069	63.894	282.225
6	2016	18.336	18.815	39.602	404.330
7	2017	18.474	10.974	13.291	389.299
8	2018	14.673	9.163	21.757	376.765
9	2019	16.503	8.832	26.417	477.608
10	2020	19.510	4.627	11.726	455.892
11	2021	11.545	4.793	11.047	843.748
12	2022	14.971	3.856	30.952	1.306.116
13	2023	6.620	3.073	29.870	1.316.731

Figure 1. Recovery amounts from waste

The district-based water consumption dataset by the Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM). contains official records organized by district and year (ULUSAV, 2024). Figure 2 displays the contents of the features of the dataset: the annual water consumption data, measured in cubic meters (m³), for 39 districts between 2015 and 2022 (ULUSAV, 2024). Both datasets are publicly accessible.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
İlçe	2022 (Tüketim-m3)	2021 (Tüketim-m3)	2020 (Tüketim-m3)	2019 (Tüketim-m3)	2018 (Tüketim-m3)	2017 (Tüketim-m3)	2016 (Tüketim-m3)	2015 (Tüketim-m3)	2014 (Tüketim-m3)
ADALAR	1.543.403	1.435.991	1.513.070	1.371.291	1.399.182	1.366.581	1.472.276	1.432.494	
ARNAVUTKÖY	18.891.299	17.102.127	15.570.466	13.818.204	11.404.878	10.176.132	9.178.953	8.002.123	
ATAŞEHİR	24.377.611	24.281.319	23.737.630	22.428.468	21.496.185	21.205.911	19.974.997	18.597.049	
AVCILAR	21.556.002	20.690.506	20.824.893	19.485.453	18.312.736	17.558.403	17.052.253	16.220.476	
B.ÇEKMECE	17.412.198	16.167.480	16.015.731	13.606.571	12.222.470	11.172.787	10.788.924	9.915.435	
BAHÇELİEVLER	29.152.163	27.729.806	29.008.190	27.841.515	26.167.510	24.868.593	24.320.533	23.610.609	
BAKIRKÖY	15.658.908	15.553.880	16.341.601	15.774.446	15.846.543	12.509.301	11.793.169	11.510.117	
BAYRAMPAŞA	14.188.089	13.716.008	14.121.835	13.630.782	13.226.158	12.516.185	11.914.393	11.545.682	
BAĞCILAR	35.848.593	34.658.417	35.237.135	32.993.615	31.241.616	29.362.186	28.182.511	26.691.720	
BAŞAKŞEHİR	31.722.402	30.164.361	27.940.128	25.124.137	21.789.720	19.576.095	18.100.255	16.174.934	
BEYKOZ	14.201.827	14.309.594	14.110.935	12.651.607	12.018.646	11.331.655	10.891.434	10.254.740	
BEYLİKDÜZÜ	22.961.265	20.415.406	20.325.425	17.387.725	16.738.110	14.948.006	13.630.387	12.346.365	
BEYOĞULLU	16.331.938	14.150.050	14.377.004	14.217.061	12.276.523	11.420.559	11.311.755	11.167.382	
BEŞİKTAŞ	15.995.329	15.485.294	15.540.651	14.877.984	13.159.182	12.609.953	12.385.216	11.976.186	
ESENLER	20.316.717	19.594.278	20.448.476	19.175.326	17.804.043	17.162.651	16.584.976	15.854.265	
ESENYURT	52.836.878	48.988.082	59.865.610	43.576.187	39.205.682	36.083.030	32.799.007	27.933.397	
EYÜPSULTAN	22.896.218	22.049.182	22.471.320	21.229.333	19.353.177	18.222.331	17.801.848	17.116.911	
FATH	28.078.147	24.965.681	25.146.679	25.804.441	23.898.917	21.983.686	21.781.211	22.358.121	
GOP	21.711.282	21.273.432	21.523.489	20.339.712	19.614.773	18.940.716	18.637.751	17.730.853	
GÜNGÖREN	14.305.999	13.788.130	14.181.195	13.925.783	13.316.278	12.769.886	12.600.044	18.994.573	
K.ÇEKMECE	38.832.413	38.030.116	38.012.294	35.731.905	33.889.979	31.994.320	31.086.665	29.188.561	
KADIKÖY	30.933.432	30.091.668	30.335.037	29.163.147	26.133.035	24.797.597	24.310.256	23.910.542	
KARTAL	25.696.738	23.426.846	24.044.402	22.120.380	21.603.458	20.375.603	20.007.459	19.155.143	
KAĞITHANE	23.152.747	21.257.865	22.615.121	20.978.127	20.103.122	19.286.724	19.030.632	18.207.418	
MALTEPE	27.824.535	26.468.078	27.235.906	26.072.596	24.122.700	22.703.875	22.794.286	21.906.064	
PENDİK	38.555.916	36.672.757	36.518.039	33.631.440	31.793.762	29.743.117	28.474.258	26.499.977	
SANCAKTEPE	21.957.759	20.714.459	20.334.753	18.066.203	16.749.300	15.239.008	14.090.151	12.313.398	
SARIYER	25.503.566	23.646.023	23.409.803	21.989.067	20.565.527	19.427.187	18.711.570	17.555.072	
SULTANBEYLİ	14.450.593	13.794.759	13.732.990	12.120.982	11.481.268	10.814.861	10.224.559	9.599.250	
SALTANGAZI	24.147.507	23.226.015	23.549.732	21.540.504	20.317.332	19.163.693	18.219.393	17.142.236	
SİLVİRİ	13.216.660	12.232.563	11.744.060	10.056.059	8.941.729	8.452.805	8.227.604	7.620.350	
TUZLA	24.758.012	32.598.699	20.495.275	16.936.290	14.956.036	13.625.147	12.690.324	11.546.080	
ZEYTİNBURNU	16.887.563	15.630.079	15.842.440	14.827.378	14.272.304	13.469.519	13.068.037	12.576.945	
ÇATALCA	4.961.608	4.853.591	5.038.009	4.080.220	3.665.598	3.311.210	3.222.450	2.931.018	
ÇEKMEKÖY	14.902.585	13.369.537	13.337.413	11.658.154	10.808.688	10.205.702	9.705.483	8.951.936	
UMRANİYE	37.618.657	35.801.227	36.324.008	33.918.205	32.858.425	31.061.816	30.065.065	28.085.173	
ÜSKÜDAR	29.904.256	29.074.076	29.491.392	28.298.739	27.205.893	26.353.986	26.110.542	25.142.059	
ŞİLE	4.247.815	3.928.416	3.962.073	2.965.979	2.522.410	2.196.246	2.098.928	1.835.302	
ŞİŞLİ	20.376.715	18.357.725	19.240.101	18.875.509	17.063.291	16.076.563	15.948.709	15.717.630	

Figure 4. District-Based Water Consumption Amounts

2.2. Open-source Libraries and Frameworks

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are built upon fundamental algorithmic principles, critical in ensuring accurate outcomes. Algorithms—defined as a series of logical steps followed to solve a problem—are used in AI applications to process data and achieve specific goals. These algorithms' effectiveness, accuracy, and performance significantly influence the learning process. The design of AI algorithms is based on core principles such as effectiveness, finiteness, definiteness, input, output, and performance.

In AI fields such as machine learning and deep learning, algorithms generate predictions and decisions based on input data. Each algorithm consists of clearly defined start and end points, with precise procedural steps, which ensure consistent results in every execution cycle. For AI systems to function successfully, algorithms must be well-defined, free from unnecessary complexity, and capable of delivering high-performance solutions. Therefore, the accurate structuring of each algorithmic step is a crucial factor in the success of AI applications.

Effective AI implementations require robust and flexible software tools. The Python programming language and its rich library ecosystem play a significant role in AI projects. Python is widely preferred in AI development due to its versatility and user-friendly nature. Particularly in data processing, modeling, and visualization, Python libraries contribute greatly to the success of AI projects.

In this context, **libraries such as Pandas and NumPy are frequently** used for data manipulation and mathematical computations, while Matplotlib is employed to graphically represent data analysis results. Scikit-learn offers a broad range of algorithms for rapidly developing machine learning models. For deep learning applications, libraries such as TensorFlow and PyTorch enable high-performance computation and model training. BeautifulSoup is utilized in web scraping tasks, allowing data to be collected and analyzed from online sources.

These Python libraries perform various tasks in AI projects, such as data processing, model building, visualizing results, and retrieving data from external sources. Each library enhances the efficiency of applications with its unique capabilities. Thanks to the functionality offered by these libraries, AI applications have become more efficient and faster, allowing problems to be solved more effectively.

2.3. AI- Models/ Deep Learning Architecture

Deep learning is an advanced machine learning method that utilizes multiple layers of nonlinear processing units, where each layer receives the output of the previous one as its input. This technique enables the learning of complex relationships in data and facilitates solving linear and nonlinear problems. Unlike traditional machine learning methods, deep learning automatically extracts features from data and builds higher-level representations (LeCun, 2015; Fırat, 2024; Turan, 2024; Zamanzadeh, 2024). Deep learning models are formed by adding one or more hidden layers to a basic single-layer neural network. The application areas of deep learning are rapidly expanding and are widely used in fields such as disease diagnosis in healthcare, autonomous vehicle control in the automotive industry, and predictive modeling in finance. Increasing parallel processing capabilities allows deep neural networks to be trained faster and more efficiently (LeCun, 2015; Turan, 2024; Zamanzadeh, 2024).

Figure 5. Structure of a Deep Neural Network

Deep learning models have added a new dimension to machine learning applications and significantly improved success rates in artificial intelligence. The power of these models stems from the number and functionality of their hidden layers, which allow them to learn more intricate relationships in the data and enhance overall model performance. Figure 5 illustrates the structure of a deep neural network, showing inputs, outputs, and various network layers (Dutka, 2023).

Among the deep learning architectures are: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs), Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBMs), Deep Belief Networks (DBNs), and Autoencoders (AEs), often referred to as the Diabolo architecture.

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2.3.1. LSTM Model Mimarisi

This section presents the LSTM model architecture used in the study. LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) is a deep learning algorithm capable of learning long-term dependencies. It is successfully applied to cybersecurity problems and tasks such as text recognition, speech recognition, and machine translation. Unlike traditional recurrent network architectures, LSTM includes input, output, and forget gates. The first step in the LSTM structure involves determining which data the model should retain or forget. The forget gate removes unnecessary information for the current context (Brownlee, 2017; Lim, 2021; Eşlik, 2024; Chen, 2025).

Time series must be transformed into supervised learning formats for use in deep learning models. One common method for this transformation is the sliding window technique, which uses previous time steps to predict the next one. The main idea of this approach is to analyze the current

time step (t) and forecast the next time step ($t + 1$). The general structure of the LSTM algorithm is shown in Figure 6 (Brownlee, 2017; Lim, 2021; Yusufoglu, 2021).

Figure 6. Basic Structure of the LSTM Algorithm

Unlike standard recurrent neural networks, LSTM has forget gates in addition to input and output layers. The first decision is whether or not to retain the incoming data. For example, during a transition between environments, if the past context is no longer relevant, the forget gate removes it from memory. This mechanism enables the model to learn long-term dependencies more effectively.

The mathematical formulation for the forget gate is given in Equation (1).

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (1)$$

The LSTM network offers a broader application spectrum than conventional recurrent neural networks. It is effectively used in large time series forecasting, music composition, and language processing tasks. The sigmoid gate, the input gate, determines which values should be updated, while the adjacent tanh gate generates a candidate vector of new values. The mathematical expressions for input gate activation and cell candidate value calculation are provided in Equations (2) and (3).

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (2)$$

$$C_t = (W_c[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c) \quad (3)$$

The complete set of operations performed within the LSTM structure is represented mathematically in Equation (4).

$$C_t = f_t \cdot C_{t-1} + i_t \cdot C_t \quad (4)$$

The LSTM output layer has two functions: the sigmoid and tanh. The role of the sigmoid function in the output gate mirrors that of the forget gate. The tanh function, represented in the output gate, produces values between -1 and 1, determining the extent of the information passed on. These calculations are shown in Equations (5) and (6).

$$\sigma_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (5)$$

$$h_t = \sigma_t \cdot \tanh(C_t) \quad (6)$$

To evaluate the prediction performance of the deep learning model, five statistical metrics were used: Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and Coefficient of Determination (R^2) (Utku, 2024; Song, 2024; Eşlik, 2024).

Equation (7): MSE measures the average squared difference between actual and predicted values, penalizing larger errors more heavily.

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - p_i)^2 \quad (7)$$

Equation (8): RMSE is the square root of MSE, converting the error into the same unit as the predicted values.

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - p_i)^2}{N}} \quad (8)$$

Equation (9): MAE computes the average of the absolute differences between predictions and actual observations.

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |o_i - p_i| \quad (9)$$

Equation (10): MAPE expresses the accuracy of predictions as a percentage, allowing comparison across datasets of different scales.

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{o_i - p_i}{o_i} \right| \times 100 \quad (10)$$

Equation (11): R^2 (coefficient of determination) evaluates the strength of the linear relationship between actual and predicted values; a score close to 1 indicates high model fit.

$$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - p_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - \bar{o})^2} \quad (11)$$

The experimental framework of this study is carried out in two phases: **(1)** preprocessing and visualizing data from both the “Recovery Amounts from Waste” and “District-Based Water Consumption” datasets to develop an analytical model, and **(2)** utilizing the “District-Based Water Consumption Amounts 2015–2022” dataset to construct a forecasting/predictive model employing the LSTM algorithm.

3 DISCUSSION

This study demonstrated the potential of leveraging open-source datasets and frameworks to streamline the process of learning, implementing, and experimenting with AI architectures through two showcase models: an analytical model and a predictive model.

In the analytical model, the "Recovery Amounts from Waste" and "District-Based Water Consumption Amounts" datasets were preprocessed, cleaned, and visualized to extract meaningful insights. The visualizations, produced using Python libraries such as Pandas and Matplotlib, successfully showcased the annual trends in waste recovery operations and water consumption patterns across Istanbul districts. The visualizations provided intuitive, graphical interpretations that highlighted key fluctuations and growth patterns over the years, offering critical support for decision-makers in environmental and urban management contexts. The ability to derive such actionable insights through simple, open-source tools emphasizes the power of combining accessible data with foundational AI techniques, without the necessity of high-cost, proprietary systems.

In the predictive model, a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) deep learning architecture was employed to forecast district-based water consumption. The model training was conducted after careful data preprocessing, normalization, and transformation into a supervised learning format. The LSTM model achieved a **training accuracy of 96.75%** and a **testing prediction accuracy of 99.038%**, with an **average test error of only 0.962%**. These results illustrate the strong capability of LSTM architectures to capture complex temporal dependencies within time series data, even when developed using entirely open-source resources. The forecasting performance metrics—including low Mean Squared Error (MSE) and high R^2 values—highlight the robustness and reliability of the predictive model.

Both experiments validate that the integration of open-source datasets, AI algorithms, and libraries facilitates rapid learning, experimentation, and deployment of AI solutions. They demonstrate that high-quality, accurate, and actionable AI models can be developed without access to private datasets or commercial software tools. Furthermore, the study underscores that the adoption of open-source resources fosters transparency, reproducibility, and inclusivity in AI research and application development, aligning with contemporary trends towards democratizing technology and accelerating digital transformation across sectors.

Future studies could build upon this foundation by comparing the performance of models trained with open-source data against those trained with proprietary datasets to further quantify the trade-offs in data quality, model generalizability, and practical deployment in real-world scenarios.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study explores the integration of open-source data, artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, and digital tools or frameworks to support learning and experimentation in applying AI architecture prior to the production stage. **It highlights the critical role of open-source resources in facilitating understanding and investigating AI architecture implementation as a solution.** The research utilized two publicly available datasets and applied a range of algorithmic and mathematical techniques using open-source software and libraries, including Scikit-learn, TensorFlow, and PyTorch, developed in programming languages like Python. As a result, two models—one analytical and one predictive—were successfully developed within a remarkably short period.

As a result, the study reached two key conclusions: (1) it provided an illustrative example demonstrating how the concept of open-source can facilitate the implementation of AI architecture, which is becoming increasingly integrated into digital solutions, and (2) the integration of open-source data and tools promotes wider adoption of AI, driving substantial sectoral transformation.

This synergy enables more efficient data analysis and application development, emphasizing the importance of effectively utilizing open data and advancing AI solutions as crucial steps in addressing technology-driven challenges. These AI-driven methodologies offer a strategic pathway toward smarter and more automated solutions..

Future research could explore the efficiency of AI models developed using open-source datasets in comparison to those created with private datasets, which are often more precise and relevant.

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